

USING FOREIGN STUDENTS IN ENRICHING THE CONTENT OF COMPARATIVE PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE.

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Abstract: Comparative pedagogy as a field of pedagogical science and the subject of study performs the important function of introducing students to education in different countries of the world and allows them to apply foreign experience in the development of domestic education. Despite the sociocultural differences that determine the specifics of education in the modern world, the trend of globalization affects everything aspects of education and training. For example, new educational Internet resources are forcing us to change the means of teaching in all countries of the world, taking into account widespread virtual self-education children and youth.

Key words: The concept of comparative pedagogy, Comparativism, the subject of comparative pedagogy, the main tasks of comparative pedagogy, the work performed by the science of comparative pedagogy.

The main part: The concept of comparative pedagogy. Comparative pedagogy or comparativistics was initially formed in the field of philosophical sciences and studied various issues, including the problems of education and upbringing of the growing young generation in the countries of the world. Even in ancient times, there was a lot of information about how children were educated in different nations and countries in the context of philosophical teachings. They summarized the educational methods and values, and analyzed the unique aspects of how life experience is passed on from the older generation to the younger generation.

In modern language, comparative pedagogy is also called comparativistics. Comparativism (lat. comparatavis-comparative) means to compare and contrast, it embodies the identification of similar and different aspects of historical development trends, the separation of compatible aspects of similar phenomena. In English, —to compare| also means —to compare. As an independent philosophical concept, comparativism is used in various fields of science, as well as in literary studies, in the comparative historical analysis of the development of images and plots in the fiction literature of different nations. In the theory of education, the concept of "comparative studies" is synonymous with the concept of comparative pedagogy. Therefore, it is not a mistake to call this field of pedagogy "pedagogical comparativistics".

Researchers say that foreign sources use the term "comparative education" rather than "comparative pedagogy". After all, "education." The word —education) is used in a broad sense compared to the word pedagogy (—pedagogie). According to the foreign pedagogical tradition, the word "education" means the unity of development, education and upbringing. In addition, pedagogy is used only as a concept related to the education and upbringing of children. That's why we note that in foreign definitions, the phrase "education compare" is used more often than "pedagogie comparative". We use the terms "comparative pedagogy", "pedagogical comparativistics", "comparative education" and "comparative studies" as synonyms. Because despite several different aspects, in modern pedagogical theory and practice, these concepts are often used to define exactly the same phenomena and processes. It should be noted that today the concept of "comparative pedagogy" is more widespread in Uzbekistan. In general, comparative pedagogy is considered an independent branch of pedagogy that studies the specific aspects of education, training and education in different countries. In a broad sense, comparative pedagogy is a field of science that studies the state, laws and development trends of education in different countries and regions of the world, and develops methods of mutual enrichment of the national education system through the use of foreign experience. .

If we give a more precise definition of comparative pedagogy, it is a science that, as an independent branch of pedagogy, studies the development trends, laws and conditions of pedagogy theory and practice in different states and countries of the world. It also distinguishes the corresponding and different aspects of the national and regional specificity of general trends and develops forms and methods of mutual enrichment of the national education system through foreign experience.

Each of these approaches to understanding comparative pedagogy reveals its own essence.

First, it is a specific field of pedagogy. Secondly, it is aimed at studying the development process of education, training, pedagogic theory and practice in different countries and regions of the world. Thirdly, the analysis at the level of comparative comparison is carried out to apply foreign experience to a certain extent. Fourthly, specific forms and methods of mutual enrichment of the national education system are highlighted.

The subject of comparative pedagogy is a comparative analysis of foreign and Uzbek pedagogical experience and the state, trends and development laws of modern national pedagogical culture.

The main tasks of comparative pedagogy:

- description and analysis of facts and evidence reflecting the processes of educational development in different countries;

- comparative analysis, classification and systematization of quantitative and qualitative changes in the development of education in different countries;

- reveal trends and laws of educational development in different countries;

- forecasting ways and opportunities of education development in different countries;

- comparison of educational achievements and shortcomings in foreign countries and to compare

- general analysis of the education system of foreign countries

The work of comparative pedagogy.

- coordination and regulation of terms and concepts in pedagogical documents of different countries so that it is convenient for experts to study foreign experience;

- comparison of theoretical ideas, educational policy, educational models of foreign and Uzbek pedagogues;

- forecasting the development prospects of education;

- development of education development strategy.

Comparative pedagogy studies a wide range of issues:

Not only the content and organizations of educational theory in different countries, but also educational methods, forms, tools, educational institutions, management, educational values, etc. Researches the development of education and upbringing system in different countries by comparing and comparing their similarities and differences. It compares and contrasts the educational system and its development dynamics, taking into account the cultural, historical and socio-political characteristics of a particular country.

The main categories and concepts of comparative pedagogy.

Comparative pedagogy uses general pedagogical and psychological categories and concepts: education, training, upbringing, development, socialization, etc. Specific concepts of comparative studies include comparative pedagogy, pedagogical comparativistics, world education system, national education system, globalization of education, social classes of education, strategy of education development, standardization of education, modern foreign

pedagogical experience, national education and training system, pedagogical culture, educational policy, educational trends, etc.

In this science, each nation should have its own unique national-educational culture in accordance with its way of life, historical and social level, and national culture, and should be able to use them in life. The place and importance of the science of comparative pedagogy in the process of the market economy, the formation of national ideological views of students and young people, the determination of the place and role of healthy faith as a force of the progressive authority of the society, the place and role in the process of becoming free-thinking, perfect people. Detailed information is given about the implementation and prospects of education in world pedagogy, especially in developed countries.

The French education system has a rich and ancient history. Here, the Law "On Education" was first adopted in 1955, and a number of amendments were made to it in 1975. On March 15, 2004, the new Law "On Education" was adopted

In France, the first stage of the education system is pre-school education. This stage is also known as "Mothers' School". The purpose of this is to bring children's conditions at school closer to their own conditions, to form a warm relationship with them as in a family.

In the French education system, it is very important to bring children ready for school from infancy.

The main problem in German education is to bring education in the former GDR to the same national standard. consists of casting.

But it also has its own problems. The first is the question of funds, and the second is the attitude of the participants of the educational process in the former GDR to this change.

The formation period of the Dutch education system corresponds to the period of the Batav Republic, which emerged as a result of the French Revolution in 1789. 75 percent of the country's schools are established by private individuals, organizations and societies, including Christian or Catholic churches. The education system of this country is 7-3-2. Primary education is combined with preschool education.

In the Netherlands, about 4 mln. young people receive full-time education. Compulsory education in the country is free, large youth schools and universities are paid.

Salaries of teachers and educators are determined by the state. The Ministry of Education is the most expensive ministry in the Netherlands. State to him for one year It will spend 29.6 billion guilders. This is 17 percent of the state budget. Its advanced education is very useful for this country to take an influential place on the earth.

The high flight of Japanese educational systems did not happen by itself. He also had his own crises and problems. It is appropriate to look at the historical stages of the country's pedagogical principles and educational development in order to imagine them more fully.

The classic formation of the Japanese education system dates back to the reforms implemented by the country's ruler Meiji in 1867-1868. This was the first strict slogan of the ruler, one was "Fukkoki kyoxi" - to enrich, strengthen and militarize the country, and the other was "Syokusan kogio" - to develop the country's economy based on advanced western production technology. . Meiji believed that the main factor for the realization of the two goals was the radical change and renewal of the educational systems.

Japan is a country with high scientific power. It ranks second in the world in spending money on the development of education after the United States. When the country includes the private sector in scientific research, four-fifths of the funds allocated to the development of general

science are allocated. In the next 10-15 years, higher educational institutions in the field of natural sciences and technology were developed, for which about 60% of the funds intended for scientific research will be spent.

Technical development has increased the need for high-level specialists and workers.

In developed countries, general compulsory and free education of children up to 12-13 years old has been introduced. This factor led to an increase in the literacy rate of the population, and the network of privileged educational institutions expanded. However, the majority of people lived in poverty, poor housing conditions, and the need to earn money for a living from childhood forced many children to drop out of school before completing their education. At the same time, it was impossible not to see negative aspects in the field of education.

Conclusion: Comparative pedagogy today compares the different features of development laws and trends of educational theory and practice. Comparative pedagogy provides advice on ways to update and implement the selected school policy in the country, the conditions that affect the results of the decisions made, the ability to foresee the consequences of the selected policy and the correctness of its implementation. analyzes tasks such as.

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